

Appendix A - Assessing and Refining the List of Candidate Issues

I. APPENDIX

The detailed assessment of the issues of each ML Life Cycle phase is presented in this appendix.

II. ISSUES OF THE DATA COLLECTION ML LIFE CYCLE PHASE

A. Data Integration

Example: Multiple data sources (CSV, Excel sheets, SQL databases, NoSQL databases) have to be integrated to create a unified data source.

1) Missing data integration:

Figure 1 illustrates the aggregated votes of the experts for this issue. It can be observed that its occurrence in practice leading to TD was confirmed. Its relevance was acknowledged to varying degrees, but using the median and following our criteria, it can be classified as an issue of low relevance.

Fig. 1: Missing data integration

Participant P5 gave an example: *“In the context of predictive models, a lack of data integration can lead to the absence of relevant information for the model, hampering the achievement of high accuracy. For example, in practice, a crucial explanatory column may be missing, undermining the model’s ability to adequately capture relationships between the available variables”*. Participant P8 reaffirmed the previous comment: *“There will be a possibility of future rework because, when evaluating the results, it may be challenging to explain or find a justification for the inadequate model due to the absence of a portion of the data”*.

2) Incomplete/Insufficient data integration:

Figure 2 provides the aggregated votes of the experts for this issue, leaving no doubt about its status as a highly relevant issue.

Fig. 2: Incomplete/Insufficient data integration

Participant P2 mentioned a previous experience: *“This reminded me of a situation I went through. There were two data sources. We could access one data type but often lost access to the other. To illustrate what this integration could be, we had to generate different models because we were working with only a portion of the data”*.

Participant P7 argued: *“I think it’s quite common and happens more often than simply missing (the previous issue). You consider one part and later realize that something is missing. I believe it’s more common than the first scenario because when you do nothing, you immediately see that a step in the process is missing.”*.

3) Inappropriate/Wrong data integration:

Upon analyzing the results from both sessions, Figure 3 unmistakably establishes the classification of this issue as highly relevant. In both sessions, all participants reported agreement in response to both questions.

Fig. 3: Inappropriate/Wrong data integration

Participant P6 provided an example from a project’s outset: *“In my team, we utilize a template that streamlines data integration. Before adopting this approach,*

we encountered challenges as multiple team members were tackling the same issue independently, resulting in redundant efforts”.

Participant P5 stated: “When data integration is done incompletely or inadequately, considering that the machine learning model will learn from this input data, it may not learn effectively, leading to poor accuracy. However, the impact can be even worse, as the model can learn incorrectly if data integration is done incorrectly. An improper shortcut when integrating data can lead to significantly more effort in the future.”.

B. Data consumption

Example: Data consumption problems occur when a model consumes data missing values.

1) Missing data consumption:

Figure 4 depicts the overall votes from the experts and confirms that this issue does not fall under the category of TD and can be discarded.

Participant P1 expressed skepticism about the feasibility of continuing development in this scenario, stating: “I do not see the possibility of continuing development in this case” while Participant P2 asserted that “this is a crucial step missing; it would be a bug”.

Fig. 4: Missing data consumption

2) Incomplete/Insufficient data consumption:

Figure 5 illustrates the results from both sessions. Most participants reported full agreement, leading us to conclude that this issue occurs and can be categorized as highly relevant.

Fig. 5: Incomplete/Insufficient data consumption

Participant P3 explained that “This is a challenge we often encounter, and we deal with it by filling in the gaps

by repeating the previous value, typically the standard procedure, or by applying appropriate calculations for the situation. It’s more a matter of recognizing the situation and establishing a policy to address it. A weak policy to speed delivery without providing an optimal solution may lead to technical debt.”.

Participant P5 stated: “For me, this problem is very similar to incomplete data integration, but there it involves columns, and here it relates to rows. If, by chance, the most relevant lines are the ones I did not consume, this could become a problem that would be hard to fix later.”.

3) Inappropriate/Wrong data consumption:

The results are shown in Figure 6. Since nearly all participants agreed with both statements, we can confidently conclude that this issue can be classified as highly relevant.

Fig. 6: Inappropriate/Wrong data consumption

Participant P1 made an important statement about the consequences: “I tend to believe that when something is done incorrectly, it’s much more serious for me than when it’s not done at all, and I even prefer not to do it than to do it wrong”.

Participant P8 cited a previous experience: “This has happened to me. I used a different version of the dataset to compare it with a model generated from another dataset. In theory, we wanted to compare models built with the same dataset. When we evaluated the performance, it was very poor. It wasn’t immediately obvious because the model was working.”.

III. ISSUES OF THE DATA PRE-PROCESSING ML LIFE CYCLE PHASE

A. Identification of outliers

Example: An outlier is an observation that significantly deviates from the typical or expected values within a random sample from a population. These atypical observations can be either unusually high (positive outliers) or unusually low (negative outliers) compared to most data points in the sample. Outliers can distort statistical analyses and may indicate potential errors or interesting patterns in the data. Identifying and handling outliers is an important step in data analysis to ensure the accuracy and reliability of your results.

1) Missing outlier identification:

In the first question, regarding the occurrence, all participants reported agreeing. Regarding relevance, two participants reported partial agreement in the second question, and two said they agreed.

Participant P3, referring to one of the previous issues, "Missing consuming data correctly", where it was emphasized that skipping is not advisable, mentioning that one might consider cutting it to save time, thinking it wouldn't significantly impact and, for instance, skipping the step of searching for outliers to build the model more quickly. However, this is quite serious because it can greatly influence the results. P3 said: "It's not a good step to miss. Depending on the model you intend to use, it can significantly affect its outcome, potentially ruining your results. You deal with later stages, trying to improve when the error was in the step you skipped. I mentioned that it could be a serious issue".

In the second session, in the first question, one participant reported partially agreeing, and four agreed. In the second question, two participants reported partially agreeing, and three said agreeing.

Figure 7 shows that despite not having unanimous agreement regarding its existence and relevance in both sessions, we can categorize this issue as highly relevant.

Fig. 7: Missing outlier identification

2) *Incomplete/Insufficient outlier identification:*

In the first session, all participants agreed on the question about occurrence. Regarding the question about relevance, all participants reported partially agreeing.

In the second session, the first question regarding occurrence, one participant reported partially agreeing, and four agreed. In the second question, regarding relevance, two participants reported partially agreeing, and three said agreeing.

Participant P7 exemplified: "It's possible to add more columns even after that stage. For example, if you return to the data collection phase, you might forget to adapt the code to test the new columns".

Figure 8 summarizes the consensus between the two sessions, making this issue less relevant.

Fig. 8: Incomplete/Insufficient outlier identification

3) *Inappropriate/Wrong outlier identification :*

All participants agreed on the first question about occurrence in the first session. In the second question, regarding relevance, one participant reported partially agreeing, and three said agreeing.

During the second session, all participants unanimously agreed with both questions.

Participant P6 provided feedback on your interpretation of this matter: "An example of this situation would involve considering an extended timeline. At a certain point, there was a shift in the behavior of the data, causing it to deviate from the established standard range. Consequently, we excluded this data, even though it merely represented a change in data behavior and should not have been classified as outliers".

Figure 9 shows the consensus between the two sessions in affirming the significance of this issue as highly relevant.

Fig. 9: Inappropriate/Wrong outlier identification

B. *Selecting features when needed*

Example: Feature selection is a crucial technique that carefully chooses a subset of input variables for your model while retaining only the most relevant information and eliminating noisy or less important data. This process enhances model performance and clarity.

1) *Missing features selection:*

In the first session, all participants reported to agree in the first question. In the second question, all participants reported agreeing.

In the second session, the question about occurrence, two participants reported partially disagreeing, one not sure, and two agreeing. Regarding the question about

relevance, two participants reported agreeing, and three were not sure.

Participant P5 stated: "Most feature selection is already performed by most ML algorithms by design, so not doing it is not necessarily a problem. On the other hand, there are performance concerns. In requirements engineering, unmet non-functional requirements can be more problematic than those. For instance, if the application becomes too slow, it may not be used, and in this case, it can be a significant issue".

Despite a divided vote, with some participants marking "not sure" for both questions, the prevailing sentiment is that this issue can be classified as highly relevant. This outcome is further illustrated in Figure 10.

Fig. 10: Missing features selection

2) *Incomplete/Insufficient feature selection:*

In the first session, all participants reported agreeing partially on the question regarding occurrence. Regarding the question about relevance, one participant reported partially disagreeing, and three reported partially agreeing.

Participant P1 mentioned that "Incomplete, to me, means the following: I have various approaches to feature selection. In the project I am working on, it's common for us to quickly create an initial version of the model to deliver it. Later, we refined and adjusted this model as we gained more knowledge about the problem. This can happen through data analysis or discussions with experts in the problem domain. There are several stages involved, and this constitutes a cycle.

Sometimes, we backtrack and discover that we have more data that wasn't provided to us previously. Within these stages of feature selection, one of them is especially important. We start with a specific selection and build a solid model. Then, we evaluate another selection that makes sense, analyze the importance of variables, and remove some of them to improve the models. This is done to expedite the initial delivery and then evolve from there.

The key point is that, in certain cases, people may not realize that the initial approach was insufficient, and later on, it may be necessary to revisit this stage to enhance the model".

Participant P3 said: "I think 'incomplete' is a business

decision, depending on whether it's worth investing more time in improvements or if the result is satisfactory enough. Not executing is a problem. The results of doing incomplete could probably improve later. Doing something wrong is always an issue, such as, for example, excluding an important variable."

During the second session, in both questions, two participants reported partial agreement, one agreed, and two reported being unsure.

Based on the findings from the two focus group sessions, shown in Figure 11, this issue can be categorized as low relevant as most voters cast partially agree votes.

Fig. 11: Incomplete/Insufficient feature selection

3) *Inappropriate/Wrong feature selection:*

In both sessions and questions, all participants reported agreeing.

Participant P1 mentioned that "Visualizing and identifying the problem can be challenging; it often requires time for debugging and comprehension." Participant P3 affirmed the previous comment: "This happened to me when the variables had similar names. One ended in '31,' and I mistakenly used the one ending in '33.' I spent quite some time trying to figure out why my model wasn't producing coherent results. It was frustrating"

In the second session, Participant P6 shared an experience: "This happened to me while working on a model. We had a variable for which we were missing data for an extended period, resulting in the loss of half of the information. We decided to remove this variable for that reason. However, when we presented the model to the stakeholders, we discovered that this variable was the most crucial".

Participant P5 agreed and added another example: "I've seen this happen before. We had around 150 columns, and we would ask the stakeholders to determine which ones were important. Still, we performed a preliminary cleanup to ensure they got all the information. However, during this cleanup, we removed about 100 columns. Out of those 100 pulled, approximately 30 of them should have been kept. We were trying to help but ended up causing more harm than good".

Figure 12 depicts unanimous agreement between the two sessions regarding the occurrence and relevance of this issue as highly relevant.

Fig. 12: Inappropriate/Wrong feature selection

Fig. 13: Missing missing value identification

C. Identifying missing values

Example: Missing data refers to the absence of values or information for certain variables within a given dataset.

Participant P1 provided an illustrative example of a typical approach when dealing with this topic before the participants of the first session started to discuss the first issue: "For instance, in the context of a regression problem, it's common practice to perform a process known as form filling, if the project's schedule permits. This often arises when there are numerous gaps in the dataset. However, in certain situations where we are confident that a specific variable remains relatively stable over a given time frame, we can propagate the preceding value as a solution".

1) Missing missing value identification:

In the first session, regarding the question about occurrence, three participants reported partially disagreeing, and one wrote partially agreeing. Regarding the question about relevance, one participant reported disagreeing, and three reported partially disagreeing.

Participant P2 stated: "When confronted with missing data mistakes, you typically have two scenarios: leave it unaddressed (missing) or handle it incorrectly. Rarely do you manage it incompletely".

Participant P3 stated: "It has happened to me that we needed to create a model, and I tried to do it, skipping this step. I had to backtrack because I couldn't progress, and I stopped. Therefore, in this sense, no TD was generated because it was not completed; hence, it does not fall into the category of TD".

In the case of this proposed issue, all participants agreed unanimously on both questions in the second session.

Despite the diversity of the votes, the median leads us to conclude that this issue can be considered highly relevant, as shown in Figure 13.

2) Incomplete/Insufficient missing value identification:

In the first session, the first question, two participants reported disagreeing, and two reported partially agreeing. In the second question, two participants disagreed, and two reported partially agreeing.

In the second session, all participants agreed on both questions.

Participant P5 emphasized: "Overall, a problem resulting from a step performed incompletely is challenging to identify because it can give the impression that it was both done and not done. In this case, perhaps pair programming can be helpful, as your partner may be able to spot this issue more easily. Having a checklist of steps is also very helpful".

Participant P7 exemplified: "Another example would be when values of 0 are considered empty, but in some cells, the value is -1, which has also been treated as empty. Addressing only the 0 values and not handling the -1 would be an incomplete approach".

In this focus group session, based on the data presented in Figure 14, it is reasonable to categorize this issue as highly relevant.

Fig. 14: Incomplete/Insufficient missing value identification

3) Inappropriate/Wrong missing value identification:

In the first session, in both questions, all participants reported agreeing.

Participant P1 expressed: "Usually when you encounter problems, you start looking at the end of the whole process. You question whether the model is performing well, if the model's hyper-parameters are properly tuned, and if the chosen technique is the best option. Having to go back to the pre-processing stage can be quite

challenging. So, any incorrect step in the pre-processing phase that needs correction should be taken seriously, as it can have serious repercussions”.

Participant P2 affirmed what P1 said: “The issue here is that processes are functional, which means things are working; however, the outcomes achieved are not optimal, and it’s challenging to identify the root causes precisely”.

Participant P3 said: “Imagine a form which primarily accepts text inputs. For instance, in the address field, someone entered “none.” While there is no missing data, the provided value seems irrelevant. It would have been important to recognize and address this inconsistency, which was disregarded”.

In the second session, in both questions, all participants reported agreeing.

All possible votes were in complete agreement regarding the occurrence and its relevance, and this issue can be categorized as highly relevant, as shown in Figure 15.

Fig. 15: Inappropriate/Wrong missing value identification

D. Rebalancing (typically by resampling)

Example: Resampling is a technique that entails iteratively drawing samples from the training dataset, which can be done to address issues like imbalanced data or to improve the robustness of a machine learning model.

1) Missing rebalancing:

In the first session, all participants reported partially agreeing with both questions.

In the second session, four participants reported agreeing, and one was unsure about the first question. Three participants reported partially agreeing, and two agreed with the second question.

Participant P7 argued: “Depending on the dataset, this may not be such a relevant issue”.

Participant P5 completed saying: “If you don’t perform resampling but use appropriate evaluation metrics, it may not be considered as a TD.”

Although there is divergence regarding the severity of occurrence and relevance, to some degree, all voters agreed that this issue is low relevant, as shown in Figure 16.

Fig. 16: Missing rebalancing

2) Inappropriate/Wrong rebalancing:

One participant reported partially agreeing in the first session, and three agreed with the first question. One participant reported partially disagreeing, two reported partially agreeing, and one agreed with the second question.

Participant P1 remarked: “Upon recognizing the error, it becomes necessary to revisit the data distribution and conduct an exploratory analysis. It’s crucial to understand why no results are being found, especially when limited data of this type is available for training. In other words, there’s an investigation needed to discover the error. Debugging is always a bit frustrating.”.

In the second session, all participants agreed on both questions.

Participant P5 concluded: “It can significantly result in generating incorrect data for training”.

The final result can be analyzed in Figure 17, and as a result, in these focus group sessions, this issue can be classified as highly relevant.

Fig. 17: Inappropriate/Wrong rebalancing

E. Removing inconsistent data (remove the inconsistency)

Example: Initial text pre-processing includes tasks such as eliminating white spaces and standardizing capitalization to address inconsistencies in the text data.

1) Missing removal of inconsistent data:

In the first session, in the first question, all participants reported partially agreeing. Three participants reported partially agreeing with the second question, and one said agreeing.

Participant P1 mentioned a previous experience: “In one of the projects, a situation arose where, following the

technical manual, values were identified that didn't make sense when the variables were analyzed together. It was necessary to perform a manual analysis to address this inconsistency, as it couldn't be resolved through code. An expert in the domain had to alter the data directly". In the second session, all participants unanimously agreed on both questions.

Participant P5 provided an example related to image recognition: "This issue won't lead to coding rework but will necessitate redoing all the training steps. Consider, for example, if you're working with images, and a single training cycle takes five days. If you overlook this step, intentionally or unintentionally, you'll have to undergo the entire training process again, which could pose a substantial problem".

The outcome can be analyzed using Figure 18, providing consistency to assert that this issue can be classified as highly relevant.

Fig. 18: Missing removal of inconsistent data

2) **Incomplete/Insufficient removal of inconsistent data:**

In the first session, three participants reported partially agreeing, and one said agreeing in the first question. All participants reported partially agreeing with the second question.

During the second session, all participants voted in agreement on both questions.

Participant P5 exemplified this item: "I have an interesting example of a diabetes dataset I've worked with. In this dataset, when values are missing, or columns are blank, they are filled with zeros. However, if you're unfamiliar with what each column represents, this can lead to misinterpretations. For instance, consider a column representing blood pressure; it's clear that a blood pressure of zero doesn't make sense. Imagine someone unfamiliar with the medical specifics, assuming zero is a valid value for blood pressure. This underscores the importance of deeply understanding the domain of the data you are working with".

Total outcome refers to Figure 19 for a detailed analysis. Based on this, we can categorize it as highly relevant.

Fig. 19: Incomplete/Insufficient removal of inconsistent data

3) **Inappropriate/Wrong removal of inconsistent data:**

In the first session, regarding the question about occurrence, two participants reported partially agreeing, and two said agreeing. Regarding the question about relevance, all participants reported agreeing.

In the second session, all participants agreed on both questions.

Participant P5 made a brief comment: "This scenario is quite problematic, as the improper removal of inconsistent data can lead to the loss of critical information for training".

This issue can be categorized as highly relevant since all participants agreed on its relevance. For a more comprehensive analysis of the overall results, follow Figure 20.

Fig. 20: Inappropriate/Wrong removal of inconsistent data

F. Pre-processing scaling

Example: For instance, employing normalization, standardization, and logarithmic transformation.

1) **Missing pre-processing scaling:**

In the first session, in the first question, three participants reported partially agreeing, and one said agreeing. In the second question, two participants reported partially disagreeing, one partially agreeing, and one agreeing. At this point, Participant P2 argued: "I realize that identifying TD in experimentation activities is quite abstract, mainly because there's always room for improvement. Even reaching an optimal solution is possible, but it's legitimate to question why we tested only two possibilities. Why didn't we test three, four, or as many possibilities? It's more about an opportunity for improvement".

Participant P1 continued saying "Exactly, it's an opportunity for improvement, and there is a limit to how much you should keep trying to enhance it. What's important is to consider the cost-benefit of continuing to invest in it".

In the second session, all participants unanimously agreed on both questions.

A more in-depth analysis of the final result in Figure 21 highlights that, although there may be differing opinions regarding its relevance, there is no question about its occurrence. Based on that, we can categorize this issue as highly relevant.

Fig. 21: Missing pre-processing scaling

2) *Incomplete/Insufficient pre-processing scaling:*

All participants reported partially agreeing with the first question in the first session. Two participants reported partially disagreeing, and two partially agreeing with the second question.

In the second session, all participants unanimously agreed on both questions.

Participant P5 said: "You don't necessarily need to normalize all numeric columns. You can choose to normalize just a few. For example, you might normalize a salary column with a wide range of values while leaving others unnormalized. However, if you accidentally overlook the column that should be normalized, it can lead to poor results, and you might mistakenly believe that you have the best possible model".

A more detailed examination of the outcome in Figure 22 reveals that, despite differing opinions on its relevance, there is no doubt about its occurrence. We can categorize it as highly relevant using the median.

Fig. 22: Incomplete/Insufficient pre-processing scaling

3) *Inappropriate/Wrong pre-processing scaling:*

In the first session, in both questions, all participants reported agreeing.

Participant P1 gave an example: "A simple example of incorrect scaling is to apply it to the training set, and then apply it incorrectly to the test set. This is quite wrong and a common example. Another example is applying one approach to the training set and a different one to the test set or swapping columns and rows".

One participant reported partial agreement in the second session, while four fully agreed in the first question. Similarly, one participant reported partial agreement for the second question, and four fully agreed.

Participant P5 said: "In an example where, instead of standardization, normalization was applied, machine learning algorithms have mechanisms to identify associations, which can mitigate problems. Although this is not the most appropriate approach (normalizing instead of standardizing), it is at least addressed in some way. Documenting the decisions you make is always a good practice, as it can facilitate the process if, by any chance, you need to return to this stage".

There is nearly unanimous consensus regarding its existence and relevance. For a more detailed examination of the final results, please consult Figure 23. We can categorize this issue as highly relevant based on these facts.

Fig. 23: Inappropriate/Wrong pre-processing scaling

IV. ISSUES OF THE MODEL CREATION AND TRAINING ML LIFE CYCLE PHASE

A. *Testing candidate algorithm possibilities*

Example: For Classification, regression, clustering, and association algorithms.

1) *Missing testing candidate algorithm possibilities:*

In the first session, in the first question, three participants reported partially agreeing, and one said agreeing. In the relevance question, one participant reported partially agreeing, and three reported agreeing.

In the second session, all participants agreed on both questions.

Participant P7 said: "An example that comes to mind in this regard is when someone achieves such an outstanding result right from the start that they don't explore other possibilities".

The final results depicted in Figure 24 unmistakably establish that this issue, in alignment with these focus group sessions, can be classified as highly relevant.

Fig. 24: Missing testing candidate algorithm possibilities

2) **Incomplete/Insufficient testing candidate algorithm possibilities:**

In the first session, the first question, two participants reported partially agreeing, and two said agreeing. In the second question, two participants reported partially disagreeing, and two reported partially agreeing.

In the second session, three participants reported partially agreeing, and two agreed with both questions.

Participant P5 explained your perspective: *"It's important to remember that the incomplete approach should be used cautiously because it's impossible to test all existing algorithms, many of which may not even be known. In this context, incompleteness is an inherent limitation, and it's essential to prioritize the most relevant and suitable algorithms for the given problem. The choice of algorithms to be tested depends on various factors, such as the available time and your familiarity with the algorithms"*.

In terms of occurrence, there is consensus. However, regarding relevance, it is clear that this issue has low relevance. This low priority may be explained by the comment made by participant P5, who mentioned that testing candidate algorithms will always be insufficient. Figure 25 illustrates the result.

Fig. 25: Incomplete/Insufficient testing candidate algorithm possibilities

3) **Inappropriate/Wrong exploration of candidate algorithm options:**

In the first session, the first question, one participant reported disagreeing, and three reported being unsure. In the second question, regarding relevance, all participants reported being unsure.

In the second session, both questions yielded identical results: two participants reported partial agreement, while three fully agreed.

Participant P5 stated: *"Handling it inappropriately can lead to a more complex code, but it's likely that the final result won't be significantly compromised"*.

Many participants marked "not sure" regarding the occurrence and relevance in the first session, suggesting we can rule out this issue. Furthermore, the partial agreement of two voters in the second session, both in terms of occurrence and relevance, reinforces this conclusion.

B. **Splitting training/test/validation data**

Example: Training data selection, holdout

1) **Missing splitting training/test/validation data**

In the first session, in the question regarding occurrence, two participants reported partially disagreeing, one reported partially agreeing, and one said agreeing. In the relevance question, all reported agreeing.

Participant P3 said: *"It doesn't make much sense to a data scientist (missing case). It is a basic premise. I don't see this happening. People usually don't forget to perform the data split, and if there is an error in the split, such as data leakage from the training set to the test set, that would be a case of inappropriateness"*.

Both questions yielded identical results in the second session: all participants reported agreement.

Figure 26 suggests that, based on both sessions, this issue can be categorized as highly relevant despite some partial disagreements related to its occurrence.

Fig. 26: Missing splitting training/test/validation data

2) **Inappropriate/Wrong splitting of training/test/validation data**

In the first session, in the question regarding occurrence, two participants reported partially agreeing, and two said agreeing. In the second question, all reported agreeing.

Participant P3 gave an example: *"This is an illustrative example of this in cases involving time series. When you choose an approach that randomly separates the*

training and testing data, you are compromising the essence of this time series; this happens because, in time series, we are interested in capturing and preserving the patterns and behaviors that evolve, such as seasonality and trends.”.

Regarding the second session, all participants agreed on both questions.

The results can be examined in Figure 27, and it can be concluded that this issue can be categorized as highly relevant.

Fig. 27: Inappropriate/Wrong splitting of training/test/validation data

C. Hyperparameter tuning

Example: Adjust parameters such as C (SVM), K and distance metrics (KNN), Information gain, and Gini index (Decision Tree).

1) Missing hyperparameter tuning:

In the first session, in the question regarding occurrence, one participant reported partially agreeing, and three said agreeing. In the relevance question, one reported partially disagreeing, two reported partially agreeing, and one said agreeing.

One participant reported partially agreeing with both questions in the second session, while four expressed full agreement.

Figure 28 shows that we can categorize this issue as highly relevant, according to the discussions during the focus group sessions.

Fig. 28: Missing hyperparameter tuning

2) Incomplete/Insufficient hyperparameter tuning:

In the first session, in the first question, all participants reported partially agreeing. In the second question, two

said partially disagreeing, and two reported partially agreeing.

Participant P1 made an addendum: "It is challenging to establish an absolute criterion for determining what is considered insufficient, as the choice of approach can vary depending on the context and complexities of the problem. Determining whether something was incomplete or insufficient is difficult, as it may not necessarily result in significant TD that requires revisiting the issue. Sometimes, it may not be necessary to go back and address it".

Participant P3 said: "If you ask a data scientist, it will usually be considered insufficient because they are always looking for opportunities to continue testing and improving models".

Four participants reported partially agreeing in the second session, and one agreed with both questions.

Based on discussions from the two focus group sessions, we can categorize this issue as low relevant. The final result is shown in Figure 29.

Fig. 29: Incomplete/Insufficient hyperparameter tuning

3) Inappropriate/Wrong hyperparameter tuning:

In the first session, in the question regarding occurrence, two participants reported partially agreeing, one reported agreeing, and one reported being not sure. In the relevance question, two reported agreeing, and two reported being not sure.

Participant P1 gave an uncommon example that could happen: "It is possible to create a script to test various hyperparameters, but it can be challenging to avoid human errors, such as accidentally changing the input data or forgetting to adjust the hyperparameters for a specific algorithm. In a scenario where you have developed code to test different algorithms and hyperparameters, it can be easy to make the mistake of not consistently applying the appropriate hyperparameters to each algorithm. These situations are uncommon".

In the second session, all participants agreed with both questions.

In this case, it is possible to observe a difference in voting patterns between the first and second sessions. In the first session, votes were categorized as 'not sure'; in the second session, there was unanimous consensus on both questions that this issue is relevant. However, this

difference allows us to categorize this issue as highly relevant according to the discussions in the focus group sessions. Figure 30 reveals the final result.

Fig. 30: Inappropriate/Wrong hyperparameter tuning

V. ISSUES OF THE MODEL EVALUATION ML LIFE CYCLE PHASE

A. Choosing evaluation metric

Example: Accuracy, Confusion Matrix, AUC, Precision, Recall, F-Measure (Classification); MRSE, R-Squared (Regression).

1) *Incomplete/Insufficient evaluation metric selection:*

In the first session, the first question, three participants reported partially agreeing, and one said agreeing. In the second question, all reported agreeing.

Participant P1 stated: "For example, consider an alarm in a secret room with millions of dollars. The alarm should go off when there is no real threat and vice versa. You may not notice this aspect if you don't use the right metric. In this case, it's not about doing something wrong, but rather using an insufficient metric that doesn't provide adequate clues, making it challenging to interpret".

In the second session, the first question, three participants reported agreeing, and two said they were not sure. In the second question, two reported agreeing, and three were not sure.

Participant P5 made a statement about this case: "The use of 'incomplete' does not necessarily generate TD. It may be the case of needing to fully meet the client's needs optimally. For example, when creating a model with excellent accuracy but without considering execution time, it is possible that the client is not being served in the best way. In this scenario, there may not be a problem in the code itself but in satisfying the client's needs".

Figure 31 illustrates the conclusive outcome of the voting process for this particular issue. Based on the discussions, it can be concluded that this issue can be categorized as highly relevant. The votes on its occurrence and relevance exhibited variability, leading to this determination.

Fig. 31: Incomplete/Insufficient evaluation metric selection

2) *Inappropriate/Wrong evaluation metric selection:*

In the first question during the first session, three participants reported partially disagreeing, and one said agreeing. In the second question, all reported partially agreeing.

Participant P4 provided an example to illustrate their understanding of this concept: "Utilizing a metric designed for a different type of problem, like employing a regression metric to assess a classification problem, is unsuitable".

The outcome of the first session is intriguing. Although this issue is not considered common in practice, it is still relevant.

In the second session, both questions received equal responses from participants, with two indicating agreement and three voting being not sure. This suggests a mixed reaction to the questions, with some participants leaning towards understanding and another segment needing to be more certain.

Participant P8 said: "In my opinion, choosing the wrong metric doesn't necessarily result in a TD, but it can cause harm to the business".

The outcome is that this issue can be discarded.

B. Properly using methods for evaluating a model's performance

Example: Holdout and Cross-validation

1) *Inappropriate/ Wrong properly using methods for evaluating a model's performance:*

In the first session, in the first question, three participants reported partially agreeing, and one said agreeing. In the second question, one reported partially agreeing, and three said agreeing.

In the second session, the first question, two participants reported agreeing, and three said they were not sure. In the second question, one reported partially agreeing, one reported agreeing, and three said not sure.

Participant P5 comment: "It doesn't seem as bad as those items before".

There was only one vote fully agreeing in the first session on the first question and a relatively high number of abstentions during the second session on the same question; we can conclude that this issue can be discarded.